

A Study Of Teacher Effectiveness As Perceived By The Students Of Higher Secondary Level

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Abstract The quality of education and teaching depends on the effectiveness of the teachers. The purpose of this research is to study the effectiveness of teachers by higher secondary level students. 120 students were selected from class 11 belonging to age range 16-18 years, from the school randomly. Two questionnaires, Maudsley Personality Inventory (MPI) by Jalota, S.S. and Kapoor, S.D. and students rating of teaching effectiveness scale by Shashikala and Deshpande, were used to collect the data. Results revealed significant difference between the socio-emotional climate dimension and between the competence dimension of the teacher's effectiveness as perceived by the introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level. It is suggested to educational administrators that teaching effectiveness can be developed by in-service teachers during refresher courses. So that, they can provide the necessary facilities and makes the teaching effective.

Keywords Teacher effectiveness, socio-emotional climate, competence, Introvert students and extrovert students.

Introduction "Teacher is a student forever in his career".

The importance of the teachers in the education system is uncontested. A teacher plays a pivot role in the educational process. Without an effective teacher, entire edifice of education is shaky.

The effectiveness of an effective teacher depends on the quality of instructions that they gives to his students. An effective teacher does not generate the image of the students but helps them to create their own image by recognizing the problems of the students, making the subjects interesting for them, discipling and controlling the class and treating the students fairly. Although curriculum, class size, family etc. are the factors that help in the improvement of schools and students achievement, yet one factor that contributes significantly to student achievement is effective teacher. For quality enhancement in the secondary education of the nation, the right future teachers should be selected (appointed).

The recommendation has been made by new education policy 1986 that "The favourable attitudes, skills, newly knowledge and responsibility sense should be developed among teachers to meet the existing requirements". Therefore, the committees and commissions that come forward have made changes in teacher training from time to time.

The term teacher effectiveness made up of two words "Teacher" and 'Effectiveness'. Teacher means a person who helps students to acquire knowledge, competence and certain professional qualities for the purpose of encouraging and directing the learning experiences of learners. The word 'Teacher' refers to a person who is Talented(T), Efficient(E), Able(A), Cooperative (C), Humble(H), Enthusiastic (E) and Resourceful (R). According to Cuba and Bidwell effectiveness is a function of the congruence of expectations and behaviour. According to this definition, teacher effectiveness is also a congruence between the expected behaviour of teacher and perceived behaviour of teacher.

Personality is an important factor, which influences the child's perception about teaching effectiveness. A child is not born with a personality but develops one as a result of

continuous interaction with his environment. Therefore, not only heredity but also factors like constitutional makeup, social and cultural influences as well as experience and training etc. all affects one's personality. Thus every child has a unique and different personality. Thus as children move from one stage of development to another, their problems, behaviour patterns, psycho social needs, thinking processes and moral evaluations change and these needs and developmental task of a particular stage, and their own personality traits would determine how children of different personality would perceive the characteristics that they would like in an effective teacher.

Objective of study Following objectives have been formulated to be achieved through this study.

1. To identify the introvert students of higher secondary level.
2. To identify the extrovert students of higher secondary level.
3. To find out the significant variance between social emotional climate dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level.
4. To evaluate the significant difference between competence dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level.

Review of Literature

A study was conducted by Kaur (2017) for examined "Teacher effectiveness in relation to occupational stress and life satisfaction". Following results were found-1) male teacher educators had high effectiveness then in female teacher educators.2) teacher effectiveness was low in rural teacher educators. Further, teacher educators related to science, humanities and commerce had high, average and low teacher effectiveness respectively. Additionally, teacher educators with high occupational stress had low teacher effectiveness and educators who had high life satisfaction had high teacher effectiveness and vice versa.

Jha (2018) conducted a study on "Teacher effectiveness in relation to professional commitment and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers of Lucknow." According to this study there is a positive and significant association between teacher effectiveness and professional commitment, between professional commitment and job satisfaction, and between teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction. This revealed that teacher effectiveness, professional commitment and job satisfaction are connected to each other. Verma, Pawar, Somaiya, Kedare, Mehta, Tyagi, and Gillurkar (2020) studied "Selfie taking behaviour : personality factors, self esteem and interpersonal closeness in college going students in a metropolitan city." Results revealed that the tendency of selfie taking behaviour was 28.7%. People who take selfies have extroverted behaviour. No significant difference was found on other domains. It has also been seen that the behaviour of taking selfie has hindered the social and academic performance of pupils.

Sehjal, Grewal and Kumar (2021) analysed "Teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to their attitude towards information technology". The findings indicated that, for both significance levels, there is no discernible correlation between secondary school teachers' attitudes towards information technology and their effectiveness as teachers. Male and female secondary school instructors are equally effective at teaching. There is no discernible difference between them. Secondary school instructors, male and female, have similar attitudes towards information technology.

Raju and Vardhini (2022) conducted "A study on teacher effectiveness among secondary school teachers". According to the study OBC, BC, SC, and ST community teachers differ significantly from one another in terms of their effectiveness as teachers. 2) When it comes to their effectiveness as teachers, secondary school teachers employed in rural and urban areas differ considerably. Regarding teaching effectiveness, there is a notable distinction between married and single secondary school teachers. The effectiveness of secondary school teachers varies significantly based on their teaching experience. The mean scores of teacher effectiveness among secondary school teachers do not exhibit a statistically significant difference according to the type of school.

Khandelwal and Jha (2022) carried out an investigation "Teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction: A comparative study on undergraduate college teachers during online education process". The studies conclusions showed as compared to their private counterparts, government UG college instructors are considerably more effective teachers, and during the online learning process, government UG college professors report higher levels of job satisfaction.

Babu and Sundari (2023) have worked on "Teacher effectiveness of high school teachers". The research discovered that the effectiveness of high school teachers was highly impacted by both gender and the type of institution. And also discovered that

neither the teaching medium nor the classroom location had a discernible impact on the effectiveness of high school instructors.

Hypothesis On the basis of the objectives the following hypothesis have been formulated and started in null form.

- 1) There is no significant variation between socio-emotional climate dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level.
- 2) There is no significant variation between competence dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level.

Methodology In order to achieve the objectives of the study normative survey method is used. This method is also known as descriptive research. Descriptive research describes “what is”, it involves description, recording, analysis and interpretations of conditions that now exist.

Sample of the study: The sample for the investigation comprises of 120 students from class XIth belonging to age group of 16 to 18 years, were taken from the school randomly.

Variables involved and tool used: The variables which have been used in the study are-

Independence variable- Personality trait of students (extrovert and introvert).

Dependent variable- Teacher effectiveness as perceived by students.

To measure each one of these variables the following tools have employed-

Maudsley Personality Inventory (MPI) by S.S. Jalota and S.D. Kapoor.

Students Rating of Teaching Effectiveness Scale by Dr. Shashikala and Deshpande.

Statistical Techniques -In order to achieve the objectives of the study and testing hypothesis mean, SD and t-test techniques were used.

Analysis Hypothesis 1 states, “There is no significant difference between socio emotional climate dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level”.

This hypothesis has been tested by applying ‘t-test’ because the nature of the data that has been obtained in the study was such that it could be analyzed by using this statistical technique. The result has been reported in the table given below:-

Table number 1:- Showing study of the frequency of responses on the socio-emotional dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students.

Dimension of Teacher Effectiveness	Category of Students				Calculated value of ‘t’	Level of Significance
	Extrovert (N ₁ =60)		Introvert (N ₂ =60)			
	Mean (M ₁)	Standard Deviation (SD ₁)	Mean (M ₂)	Standard Deviation (SD ₂)		
Socio-Emotional Climate	85.16	21.28	74.74	15.48	3.07	* **

* Significant at 0.05 level.

** Significant at 0.01 level.

Table 1 shows a significant difference between the socio-emotional climate dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students. Minimum significant ‘t’ value is 1.98 at 0.05 level of confidence and 2.62 at 0.01 level of confidence for (degree of freedom) df 118. Obtained value of ‘t’ is 3.07 which is significant at both levels. The supposition can be drawn from the above table is that there is a significant variance between the socio-emotional climate dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level. Thus, null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2 States, “There is no significant variance between the competence dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students of higher secondary level”.

The result has been reported in the table given below:-

Table number 2 showing study of the frequency of responses on the competence dimension of teacher effectiveness as perceived by introvert and extrovert students.

Dimension of Teacher Effectiveness	Category of Students				Calculated value of 't'	Level of Significance
	Extrovert (N ₁ =60)		Introvert (N ₂ =60)			
	Mean (M ₁)	Standard Deviation (SD ₁)	Mean (M ₂)	Standard Deviation (SD ₂)		
Competence	40.66	5.90	37.12	6.58	3.07	* **

* Significant at 0.05 level.

** Significant at 0.01 level.

Minimum significant t-value is 1.98 at 0.05 level of confidence and 2.62 at 0.01 level of confidence for degree of freedom 118. The obtained calculated value 3.07 is meaningful at both level as illustrated by the table. The inference can be drawn from the above table is that there is meaningful difference between the competence dimension of the teacher's effectiveness as perceived by the extravert and introvert students. Thus, null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion The first hypothesis of the study was tested by t-test for significant difference. The inference can be drawn from this significant difference is that socio-emotional climate dimension of teacher effectiveness refers to teacher-student relationship and openness between them. As the extrovert students are more friendly, social and able to communicate their feelings easily. Therefore, they have a better perception about the socio-emotional climate dimension of that teacher effectiveness than the introvert students.

The conclusion from the second hypothesis finding can be drawn that, both the extrovert and introvert feel that the teacher is able to present the subject matter effectively and has a command over his/ her subjects. They both are more or less equally perceived by the competency dimension of teacher effectiveness in a better way, it also reveals that the extrovert and introvert dimension of the personality do not influence the perception of the students about the competency dimension of teacher effectiveness.

Educational Implications:- The finding of the study will be helpful to educational administration in understanding the need of effective teacher in in-service training programs. The dimension of teaching effectiveness in the present study can be developed by the in-service teaching during refresher courses they undergo.

Limitation of the Study Delimitations of the study are as follows-

1. The study is delimited to only higher secondary level of students of 11th class only one school of U.P. board of Meerut city.
2. The study is delimited by taking only one dimension of personality i.e. extroversion and introversion.

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